

ISic1490

I.Sicily inscription 1490

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Morgantina

Place of origin (modern)

Morgantina

Provenance

Theatre

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Morgantina, in situ

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644996

Bibliography

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Antonaccio, C. M. 1999. An inscribed stele from archaic Morgantina. *Kadmos*. 38: 87-96. At 88 n.2

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